

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING EXPERIMENTAL WORKS TO CREATE INTEREST IN LIBRARY CULTURE IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *It will be possible to develop effective options for the content of the process of formation of interest in examples of development of reading culture among students.*

Keywords: *interest, scientific and technical models, game models, simulation models, modern information technology, assessment technology.*

Experiments on the development of reading culture of students in higher education institutions, the stability of pedagogical opportunities, the consideration of the educational process of the higher education institution and the potential of students, the conditions of the experimental areas, the development of criteria and indicators for determining the level of use of the works of great figures, and the development of results and indicators output and analysis of the result were determined by the relevance of ensuring the interaction of educational content and educational tasks.

Based on the experimental program, development of methodological support for experimental works, determination of criteria for the organization of experimental exercises, determination of experimental results and methods, development of the resulting algorithm of pilot-te experimental works, analysis of received empirical data based on quantitative and qualitative indicators and generalization works were carried out on a theoretical basis.

In the course of the research, monitoring of the activities of students of higher educational institutions, questionnaire questions, tests, interviews, debates, lectures, conferences, seminars and trainings were organized with the participation of respondents-students. The degree of improvement of the didactic system of using pedagogical values was determined based on predetermined criteria. In accordance with the set goal, the experimental work had a staged nature, and specific tasks were performed at each stage. The purpose, content and methods of the study are presented in the introduction.

In the first analytical-research cycle (2018-2019), historical, pedagogical and scientific-methodical literature on improving the didactic system of using historical, scientific-pedagogical values of great figures in higher education institutions was studied and analyzed.

The state of organizing and carrying out the educational process for the development of reading culture of students in higher education institutions was analyzed and its importance in the higher education educational process was studied. It was shown that organizing and conducting the educational process on improving the didactic system of using the historical, scientific-pedagogical values of great figures in higher education institutions is a scientific methodical problem. At the stage of researching the purpose, tasks, and theoretical and practical significance of pedagogical research, a proposal was developed to improve the didactic system of using the historical, scientific [46]-pedagogical values of great figures in higher education institutions, and to organize and transfer this experience to the educational process of higher

education institutions. This questionnaire was conducted among the students of the educational direction 5111700 - "Primary education and sports educational work" in the designated higher education institutions.

The results of the conducted survey show that in the process of education in higher education institutions, various difficulties were encountered in the process of improving the didactic system of using the historical, scientific and pedagogical values of great figures. In the course of the lesson, it became known that the teachers rarely use didactic tools to improve the didactic system of using the historical, scientific and pedagogical values of great figures, and do not make the lessons interesting by dividing the time correctly.

The recommended methodical proposals and the created textbook were presented to the students of the selected HEIs for discussion, consideration of achievements and shortcomings. The suggestions, objections and opinions received from all the students were studied. Taking into account their opinions, relevant conclusions were drawn.

In the second formative stage of the research (2019-2020), the content, form, and methods of the training organized in higher educational institutions to improve the didactic system of using the historical, scientific-pedagogical values of great figures were developed. Including, the process of developing the reading culture of students was organized based on a methodical approach. The existing methods were analyzed and summarized in the training sessions, and unified general methodological instructions were developed for developing the reading culture of students. In the educational process of higher education institutions, the use of historical sources [95], familiarization with the works of foreign and national scientists, tools aimed at developing creative thinking skills were widely used, put into practice, and tested in the educational process of higher education institutions.

Also, in the experimental groups of the selected higher education institutions, seminar trainings aimed at developing the reading culture of students in higher education institutions were organized, and the process of completing tasks was monitored.

Difficulties in completing tasks, encountered problems were written down. In the course of activities organized in higher education institutions to develop the reading culture of students using the historical, scientific and pedagogical values of great figures, oral surveys and conversations were held aimed at developing positive qualities such as patriotism, pride in the culture and history of one's nation, along with pedagogical preparation, and their results were analyzed.

In the third - final phase (2020-2021), the results of the pedagogical experiment were summarized and analyzed, the research results and the compatibility of the created methods were checked in the context of the scientific and methodological developments during the educational process. Conclusions of the research were developed, and recommendations were proposed for the development of reading culture of students in higher education institutions.

During the research, experimental and control groups were formed from respondents involved in experimental work. A total of 458 respondent-students from the educational direction of "Primary education and sports educational work" of HEIs were involved in the experimental work.

A total of 458 respondents-students involved in experimental work were divided into experimental and control groups in the following number according to the principle of random selection:

- 1) 228 people in experimental groups;
- 2) 230 people in control groups.

The program "Using historical, scientific-pedagogical values of great figures" developed by us in the organization of experimental work on the development of reading culture of students in the educational direction of "Primary education and sports educational work" of selected higher educational institutions was improved based on the conclusions obtained in the course of our research work, and the experience of students in the groups was directly tested, and in the control groups, work was carried out in the usual order, based on the traditional work plan.

The following evaluation levels were developed to assess the knowledge of students in the development of reading culture in the experimental and control groups.

Table 3.2

Rating levels and indicators

Rating levels	Indicators of students' knowledge, skills and qualifications for the use of historical, scientific and pedagogical values.
High	how the knowledge, skills and qualifications of students should be at a high level in order to develop the reading culture of students.
Medium	what knowledge, skills and qualifications of students should be at the secondary level to develop the reading culture of students
Low	What low level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students should be to develop the reading culture of students, in general, why do we set this level?

The results of experimental work on the development of reading culture of students in selected groups were carried out in two stages. In the first stage, preliminary tests were conducted on students' use of historical, scientific-pedagogical values of great figures, and the results were presented in the following table.

Table 3.2

Preliminary results

№	HEIs	Groups	Nu mbe r	Rating levels					
				high		medium		low	
				in numbers	%	in numbers	%	in numbers	%
1	Jizzakh State Pedagogical Institute	experimental	76	5	6,6%	32	42,1%	39	51,3%
		control	78	6	7,7%	31	39,7%	41	52,6%
2	Tashkent State Pedagogical University	experimental	77	6	7,8%	33	42,9%	38	49,4%
		control	76	7	9,2%	32	42,1%	37	48,7%

3	Kokand State Pedagogical Institute	experimental	75	6	8,0%	35	46,7%	34	45,3%
		control	76	6	7,9%	36	47,4%	34	44,7%
General		experimental	228	17	7,5%	100	43,9%	111	48,7%
		control	230	19	8,3%	99	43,0%	112	48,7%

According to these results, let's describe the view of the diagram on the method of evaluation of the development of reading culture of students:

Figure 1. Results of mastering at the initial stage

According to the numerical data in the table and the percentage data in the diagram, the low level is 48.7% in the experimental and control groups, the middle level is 43.9% and 43.1%, respectively, and the high level is 7.5% in the experimental groups and 8.3% - in the control groups. This means that the initially determined results at the beginning of the experiment are almost close to each other.

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